

Vanillydene-Aniline Complexes of Bivalent Zinc, Cadmium and Mercury

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The solid complexes of Zn (II), Cd (II) and Hg (II) with vanillydene-aniline ligand have been prepared. The complexes are amorphous and deep yellow to pale yellow in colour. The elemental analysis shows that these are 1 : 1 adducts. The conductivity shows them to be non-electrolytes in DMF. The electronic and i.r. spectra are reported and discussed. All these studies indicate that the complexes are dimers.

SCHIFF bases derived from the reaction of salicylaldehyde with primary amines represent an important series of ligands, the metal complexes of which have been widely studied earlier¹⁻³. Although Biradar *et al.*⁴ have reported tetradentate vanillydene-amine Co(II) complexes recently, no such type (A) complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) ions have been described in the literature. The present paper reports the conductivity, electronic and infrared spectral behaviour of the Zn (II), Cd (II) and Hg(II) complexes with vanillydene-aniline Schiff base.

Experimental

All chemicals used were either Analar or of chemically pure quality.

Schiff base was prepared by condensing vanillin with aniline, in stoichiometric quantities in ethanol and the Schiff base obtained was recrystallised from ethanol and dried in vacuum at room temperature.

Preparation of Complexes : The Zn (II), Cd (II), and Hg (II) complexes were prepared by treating the Schiff base with corresponding metal (II) chloride in appropriate molar ratio in ethanol. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 3 hrs. The resulting precipitate of the complexes was filtered, washed with dry ethanol and dried in vacuum desiccator. These complexes were insoluble in common organic solvents. The complexes therefore, were purified by subjecting to Soxhlet extraction in dry ethanol to remove excess of ligand and dried in vacuum (yield 60-80%).

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Analysis

Zinc and cadmium were estimated by standard edta method⁵ and mercury was estimated by α -nitroso- β -naphthol⁶, nitrogen by Kjeldahl method and chloride as AgCl. The results of analysis are shown in Table 1.

Physical Measurements : The electronic spectra of all the complexes in DMF were obtained with Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer model H-700, using 1 cm. matched quartz cells. The conductivity measurements in DMF were made with Elico conductivity bridge having cell constant of 0.830 cm⁻¹. The i.r. spectra of the solid complexes in Nujol mull were recorded on Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Examination of results given in Table 1 shows that Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) chloride can form 1 : 1 adducts. All the complexes under study are deep yellow to pale yellow in colour, amorphous and insoluble in many common organic solvents. They are soluble in dimethyl formamide and dimethyl sulfoxide, although the solubility is not high. The concentrated acids decompose them and aqueous alkali solutions hydrolyse. All of them are stable at room temperature in solution as well as in the solid state.

Conductivity :

The molar conductance values of the complexes indicate that these behave as non-electrolytes in DMF⁷. The observed very low conductance may be due to the partial solvolysis of the complexes in DMF.

Electronic Spectra :

The absorption spectra of the Schiff base is characterized by two band maxima in the region 300-320 nm and an additional band maximum in 270-300 nm

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA

No.	Composition of complex	Empirical formula	Metal %		N %		Cl %	
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	ZnCl ₂ : L	(C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂) ZnCl ₂	18.50	18.10	3.60	3.85	19.57	19.55
2.	CdCl ₂ : L	(C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂) CdCl ₂	27.23	27.40	3.10	3.40	17.42	17.20
3.	HgCl ₂ : L	(C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₂) HgCl ₂	40.02	40.25	2.69	2.81	15.85	15.95

region. The ligand also possesses characteristic band maximum in the region 240–260 nm.

The intense band of the ligand in the region 270–300 nm and 300–320 nm are shifted by more complicated bands of varying intensities when it is coordinated with the metal ions. The spectra of the complexes do not resemble the spectra of the ligand. This is an evidence for the complex formation.

The band in the region 240–260 nm appearing in the ligand as well as in the complexes can be considered as $\pi-\pi^*$ benzenoid band in view of the assignment made by Chatterjee and Douglas⁸.

Infrared Spectra :

Infrared frequencies along with their tentative assignments are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—INFRARED DATA

Vanilly-dene-aniline Ligand	Zinc (II) complex	Cadmium (II) complex	Mercury (II) complex	Assignment (Frequency cm ⁻¹)
3150	3320 3130 3030	3350 3140 3010	3420 3210 3105	N-H stretching vibration.
1590	1655	1640 1600	1620	C = N stretching vibration.
1505 1465	1605 1530 1490 1450	1590 1580 1505 1450	1590 1550 1530 1440	Aromatic C = C vibration.
1285	1280 1245	1285 1250	1280 1250	C-O stretching vibration.
1205 1155 1115 1075 1030 1005	1235 1205 1185 1150 1040 1015	1215 1190 1165 1135 1070 1010	1210 1175 1110 1090 1040	Aromatic inplane deformation vibration.
875 860	870 830	875 825	880 830	= CH out of plane vibration.
815 770 740	760 700	750 735	775 720	Aromatic CH out of plane vibration.

A broad band appearing in the region 2700–3100 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the intramolecular hydrogen bonded OH. This assignment agrees with the previous work⁹.

A strong band around 1590 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the C = N stretch of the free Schiff base and that found in the region 1655–1620 cm⁻¹ for the complexes. This frequency shift suggests the coordination through the azomethine nitrogen.

The strong band found around 1290–1250 cm⁻¹ in the ligand and its complexes is assigned to the phenolic C-O stretching vibration. The band assignment agrees well with that made by Kovacic¹⁰.

Similarly, aromatic inplane deformation vibration bands between 1225 and 960 cm⁻¹, = CH out of plane vibration bands near 860 cm⁻¹ and aromatic CH out of plane vibration bands between 860 and 735 cm⁻¹(11) in the ligand do not resemble the i.r. spectra of complexes (Table 2) which is another evidence for complex formation.

The above observations lead us to the following conclusions :

1. The band attributable to the intra molecular hydrogen bonded OH has not disappeared in the complexes and phenolic C-O vibration shows negligible shift. This makes us to believe that -OH of the ligand has not taken part in the complex formation. The elemental analysis supports the above statement.

2. The shift of the C = N stretching vibration to the higher frequency indicates the possible coordination through the nitrogen of the azomethine group to the metal ion.

3. The complexes are non-electrolytes in nature

Taking into consideration the above points, i.e., analysis, non-electrolytic nature and spectral evidence and the usual tetravalency of M(II) (M = Zn, Cd and Hg), we propose the following structure, which can be interpreted in terms of halogen bridged dimeric tetrahedral configuration. This agrees with previous works^{12–14}.

where L = Ligand, M = Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II); X = Cl.

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